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2 **Water-Energy-Ecosystem Nexus: Balancing Competing Interests at a Run-of-**
3 **River Hydropower Plant Coupling a Hydrologic–Ecohydraulic Approach**
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5 **Alban Kuriqi¹, António N. Pinheiro¹, Alvaro Sordo-Ward², Luis Garrote²**

6 ¹CERIS, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisbon, Portugal,

7 e-mail: alban.kuriqi@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

8 ² Departamento de Ingeniería Civil: Hidráulica, Energía y Medio Ambiente, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
9 (UPM), Spain

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11
12 **Abstract**

13 The water-energy-ecosystem nexus demonstrates complex implications that depend on the
14 flow regime type. Inadequate environmental flows setting may adversely affect the riverine
15 ecosystem and/or hydropower revenue. To address this issue quantitatively, we considered
16 a run-of-river hydropower plant located in a river of the Tagus basin characterised by a
17 pluvial winter flow regime. We integrated a hydropower, a hydrologic, and an ecohydraulic
18 model to estimate the influence of nine hydrologically-based environmental flow methods
19 on hydropower production, hydrologic alteration and fish habitat. The target fish species
20 was a native cyprinid fish species, the Iberian barbel (*Luciobarbus bocagei*), considering three
21 life-stages. Results show that high environmental flow releases did not necessarily provide
22 the highest habitat availability and suitability at all seasons and fish life-stages. The adult life-
23 stage resulted in being more vulnerable to water diversion, particularly during Spring season.
24 Shallow-water hydromorphological units suffered the highest habitat loss. Some of the
25 environmental flow methods demonstrated inconsistent results over seasons and fish life-
26 stages by either allowing for higher e-flow releases whereas highly restricting hydropower
27 production or vice versa. However, results also suggest that combined and dynamic
28 environmental flow methods allow for reasonable hydropower production while inducing
29 less than 50% habitat loss and flow alteration, regarding the three life-stages over all-
30 seasons. This study contributes to the identification of the relationship between conflicting
31 objectives. Also, it provides strategic recommendations on energy-ecosystem regulation for
32 sustainable hydropower operation. This study also highlights the importance of considering
33 seasonal flow discharge variability when analysing the water-energy-ecosystem nexus.

34
35 **Keywords:** Ecological impacts; Ecological flows; Energy maximisation; Hydrologic
36 alteration; Renewable energy; Small hydropower.

Nomenclature	
A. Abbreviations and acronyms in alphabetic order	
<i>%Q-Daily:</i>	% of Mean Daily flow, [m^3s^{-1}]
<i>1/3 ASF:</i>	1/3 of the Average Summer Flow, [m^3s^{-1}]
<i>C_cSI:</i>	Channel Suitability Index related cover, [-]
<i>C_sSI:</i>	Channel Suitability Index related substrate, [-]
<i>CSI:</i>	Composite Suitability Index, [-]
<i>DSI:</i>	Depth Suitability Index, [-]
<i>e-flows:</i>	Environmental flows, [m^3s^{-1}]
<i>EFC</i>	Environmental Flow Components
<i>EFM:</i>	Environmental Flow Method
<i>HMUs:</i>	Hydromorphological Units
<i>HSCs:</i>	Habitat Suitability Curves, [-]
<i>IHA:</i>	Indicators of Hydrologic Alteration
<i>MAF:</i>	Mean Annual Flow, [m^3s^{-1}]
<i>MME:</i>	Mean Monthly Flow, [m^3s^{-1}]
<i>NFR:</i>	Natural Flow Regime, [m^3s^{-1}]
<i>RoR:</i>	Run-of-River hydropower plant
<i>SHP:</i>	Small Hydropower Plant
<i>VSI:</i>	Velocity Suitability Index, [-]
<i>WUA:</i>	Weighted Usable Area, [m^2]
B. Indices	
<i>#HI_{i,j}:</i>	Number of Hydrological Indicators for each group, [-]
<i>HI_{i,j} afr:</i>	Hydrological Indicator related to the altered flow regime, [-]
<i>HI_{i,j} nfr:</i>	Hydrological Indicator related to the natural flow regime, [-]
<i>I_{i,j}:</i>	Alteration Index regarding hydrological indicators <i>i</i> for each group <i>j</i> , [-]
<i>I_{RF}:</i>	Rate and Frequency alteration Index, [-]
<i>I_{FD}:</i>	Frequency and Duration alteration Index, [-]
<i>I_{MDE}:</i>	Magnitude and Duration of Extreme flow alteration Index, [-]
<i>I_{MM}:</i>	Mean Monthly flow alteration Index, [-]
<i>I_{TE}:</i>	Timing of Extreme flow alteration Index, [-]
<i>Q₇₅, Q₉₅:</i>	Percentiles exceedance of flow duration curve, [m^3s^{-1}]
C. Parameters	
<i>A_i:</i>	Area of the <i>i</i> th cell, [m^2]
<i>d_y:</i>	Number of days in a year, [365]
<i>H:</i>	Water depth, [m]
<i>H_g:</i>	Gross head, [m]
<i>H_{net}:</i>	Net head, [m]
<i>γ:</i>	The unit weight of water, [Nm^{-3}]
<i>L:</i>	Diversion length, [m]
<i>η_{el}:</i>	Electrical efficiency, [%]
<i>η_g:</i>	Generator efficiency, [%]
<i>P:</i>	Installed power capacity, [MW]
<i>Q_{tech}:</i>	Minimum technical operation flow, [m^3s^{-1}]
<i>ρ:</i>	Water density, [kgm^{-3}]
<i>τ_h:</i>	Operating hours, [h]
E. Variables	
<i>E (t):</i>	Energy generation, [GWh]
<i>Δt:</i>	Time, [days]
<i>τ_{ij}:</i>	Shear stress forces, [Pa]
<i>η_{tj}:</i>	Turbine efficiency, [%]
<i>S_{fi}:</i>	Friction slopes according to <i>y</i> direction, [m/m]
<i>S_{0i}:</i>	Friction slopes according to <i>x</i> direction, [m/m]

$Q_{afr}(t)$:	Altered flow regime, [m^3s^{-1}]
$Q_{env}(t)$:	Environmental flows, [m^3s^{-1}]
$q_{d_j}(t)$:	Mean daily turbine inflow for the j^{th} turbine, [m^3s^{-1}]
Q_{d_j} :	Design discharge for the j^{th} turbine, [m^3s^{-1}]
$Q_{hydro}(t)$	Available flow for energy generation, [m^3s^{-1}]
Q_{mean}	Mean flow, [m^3s^{-1}]
$Q_{mfr}(t)$	The minimum e-flow regime, [m^3s^{-1}]
$Q_{nfr}(t)$	Natural flow regime, [m^3s^{-1}]
q_x	Unit discharges according to x direction, [m^3s^{-1}]
q_y	Unit discharges according to y direction, [m^3s^{-1}]
U	Depth-averaged velocity according to x direction, [ms-1]
V	Depth-averaged velocity according to y direction, [ms-1]

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65 1 Introduction

66 Among several renewable energy sources, hydropower plays an indispensable role in the
67 global electricity grid system by constituting $\approx 17\%$ of the total electricity generation on a
68 global scale [1]. Also, hydropower plays an essential role in reducing greenhouse gas
69 emissions by avoiding daily combustion of more than 4 million barrels of oil [2]. Notably,
70 large hydropower plants with intra/interannual regulation offer several advantages
71 compared to other types of hydropower plants, such as rapid response to the grid, flexibility
72 and compatibility in providing electricity production when it is needed and enable
73 deployment of other intermittent renewable energy sources [2]. However, most of the
74 suitable sites for such type of hydropower plants have been already developed [3]. In
75 addition, the development of large hydropower plants is associated with significantly high
76 economic, environmental and social costs during their life cycle, i.e., development,
77 operation, and maintenance.

78 Furthermore, long-term regulation-based hydropower plants are being criticised for not
79 being fully sustainable; they alter natural river flow regime [4] and seasonality [5] and may
80 cause enormous adverse impacts on the riverine ecosystem, notably during hydropeaking
81 [6, 7]. Nevertheless, there is an increasing societal, economic and institutional pressure to
82 reduce further exploitation of non-renewable energy sources because of their irreversible
83 environmental impacts, and increasing the share of renewable sources [8, 9]. In this regard,
84 the European Union has set very ambitious goals by aiming to reduce the greenhouses gases
85 emissions up to 95% by 2050 [10]. On the other side, many developing countries are striving
86 to increase electrification coverage over the country and boosting their industries as well.
87 Thus, the development of Small Hydropower Plants (SHPs), mainly, those of Run-of-River
88 (RoR) type has gained considerable attention worldwide [11]. Therefore, many governments
89 provide subsidies to the public/private companies, investors and other stakeholders for
90 retrofitting or developing new SHPs. Small hydropower represents an important renewable
91 energy technology for the electrification of the rural areas and sustainable industrial
92 expansion as well. Nevertheless, only about 36% of potential SHPs has been exploited on a
93 global scale [1, 12]. Europe is leading with the highest development rate, more than 48% of
94 the total potential capacity is already installed, while China is the leading country in the world
95 in terms of installing and planned number of SHPs [1, 12]. Electricity production from SHPs on
96 a global scale constitutes approximately 7% of total renewable energy production and is the
97 third most developed renewable energy technology after large hydropower and solar power
98 plants [12].

99 In contrast to the large hydropower plants, efficiency and profitability of SHPs rely solely
100 on water availability at the time; higher flow variability leads to lower efficiency of SHPs.
101 Therefore, in such conditions, to guarantee the predicted profitability, multiple turbines of
102 different sizes may be installed in the same SHP. Nevertheless, overexploitation of available
103 water, particularly, during low flow periods may impair the riverine ecosystem [13, 14].
104 There is evidence that SHPs, including RoR ones, induce fragmentation of the fish population

105 [15] and impairs invertebrates assemblage [16], affects longitudinal connectivity and
106 reduces lotic habitat [14], may cause hydropeaking, even though at low intensity [17, 18],
107 affect the riparian patches [19], and may alter sediment transport among others [20].

108 Environmental flows (e-flows) are instrumental in mitigating the ecological impacts of
109 hydropower plants [21, 22]. E-flows refer to the typical—*intra-annual* and *inter-annual*
110 natural flow regime variability—which describes the quality, quantity, and timing of flow
111 discharge required to preserve the ecosystem and sustain essential services upon which
112 human livelihoods and well-being depend on [23, 24]. Therefore, e-flows should be
113 considered as a constraint in water resource planning and management [25]. Nevertheless,
114 because the RoR hydropower uses only a portion of the available flow in the river, e-flows
115 are often not adequately defined or in worst cases neglected [11]. The non-appropriate e-
116 flows determination might have implications not only in the aquatic ecosystem but in the
117 hydropower profitability as well [26, 27]. Numerous methods and frameworks have been
118 developed for establishing e-flows at regulated rivers [28]. Nevertheless, because of their
119 simplicity, data availability and other economic and social aspects, hydrologically-based e-
120 flow methods (EFMs) remain the most applied ones. Hydrologically-based EFMs initially
121 developed and applied in North America represent among the first approaches for e-flows
122 implantation in regulated rivers. The first hydrologically-based EFM was Tennant or so-called
123 Montana method, which remain among the most widely used EFM mainly in North American
124 and worldwide [28]. In addition to the Tennant, there are many other hydrologically-based
125 EFMs applied globally, such as indices of flow duration curve, percentage of mean annual
126 flows, 7-day low flow event (7Q10), and among others, Range of Variability Approach (RVA)
127 which is part of Indicators of Hydrologic Alteration (IHA) software [29]. Overall,
128 hydrologically-based EFMs constituted the highest number of total recorded methodologies
129 for e-flows implementation [30]. Some of the most common hydrologically-based EFMs were
130 considered in this study, as well.

131 There are many studies related to capacity sizing [31] or multi-objective optimisation of
132 RoR hydropower plants [32, 33]. Nonetheless, little research exists on the implementation
133 of e-flows at RoR hydropower plants. Most of the available literature concerns only with the
134 influence that different hydrologically-based EFMs might have on the aquatic riverine
135 ecosystem without adequately addressing the economic impacts [34, 35]. Few references
136 are dealing with both impacts, such as comparing the influence of several hydrologically-
137 based EFMs on hydrologic alteration and hydropower revenue [26] or proposing potential
138 trade-offs between riverine conservation and economic objectives considering different flow
139 regime types [27, 36, 37].

140 Further research is needed to understand better the direct impacts that hydrologically-
141 based EFMs might have on hydropower production, hydrologic alteration and particularly,
142 on the aquatic ecosystem, e. g., fish and riparian vegetation. To the best of our knowledge,
143 there have been few studies addressing such antagonistic objectives, and specifically,
144 applied to RoR hydropower plants. This gap is addressed in this study by assessing the direct
145 impacts of several energy generation scenarios imposed by nine hydrologically-based EFMs

146 on flow alteration and native fish habitat availability/suitability for different life-stages over
147 year seasons. To do so, an integrated hydropower and hydrologic-eco-hydraulic modelling-
148 based approach were proposed. Such interdisciplinary studies provide more insights to
149 improve our understanding of the sensitivity of the water-energy-ecosystem nexus. The
150 innovative contribution of this study lies in the integration and the analysis of different
151 conflicting objectives in order to have a better understanding of multiple impacts. This study
152 also proposes new tools and recommendations that enable the sustainable development of
153 RoR hydropower plants. The primary outcomes of this study were quantified in terms of
154 seasonal: e-flow releases, flow regime alteration, hydropower production and fish habit
155 availability/suitability alteration imposed by nine EFMs.

156 The main objectives of this study were: (i) To evaluate the influence of nine hydrologically-
157 based EFMs on energy generation, e-flow releases, and fish habitat availability for three life-
158 stages at the seasonal scale, (ii) to understand which life-stage of fish was more sensitive to
159 river flow diversion regarding each season, (iii) to analyse if e-flow releases imposed by a
160 combination of two different EFMs could cause less alteration of flow regime and fish habitat
161 loss without significantly affecting hydropower production, and (iv) to examine whether
162 possible trade-offs between flow regime alteration, fish habitat and hydropower production
163 differ among them depending on EFMs and fish life-stages. The manuscript is organised as
164 follows: [Section 2](#) provides essential information about the study site, data acquisition and
165 explains the methodological approach; [Section 3](#) describes the main results; interpretation
166 and discussion of main results are presented in [Section 4](#). Finally, [Section 5](#) highlights the
167 main conclusions, recommendations and gives insights for future research.

168

169 **2 Material and Methods**

170 This study is based on an interdisciplinary analysis considering an RoR hydropower plant
171 without flow regulation. The analysis consists in the computation of long-term hydropower
172 production, e-flows, flow regime alteration and impacts on fish habitat regarding nine EFMs.
173 The detailed information about the study site, flow and fish's habitat data collection and
174 methods are presented in the sections below. Respectively, [Section 2.1](#) present brief
175 information about the study site. [Section 2.2](#) shows the methodological approach. [Section](#)
176 [2.3](#) explains how the data were obtained. Brief description of e-flows is given in [Section 2.4](#).
177 [Section 2.5](#) describes the steps in computing hydropower production and e-flows.
178 Hydrodynamic and habitat computation are described in [Section 2.6](#). [Section 2.7](#) presents
179 the methodology used to characterise flow regime alteration and habitat availability. [Section](#)
180 [2.8](#) shows the approach used to conduct the multivariate analyses. Finally, limitations of the
181 study are presented in [Section 2.9](#).

182

183 **2.1 Study site**

184

185 The planned hydropower plant on which the study was conducted is located in the middle
 186 reach of the Ocreza River (39°44'07.05"N, 7°44'16,51"W), a tributary of the Tagus River,
 187 Eastern Portugal (Fig. 1). The Ocreza River flows through schistose geological formations; the
 188 total length of the river is 94 km, and the drainage area is 1429 km². The length and drainage
 189 area of the river at the study site, upstream of the intake weir are 62 km and 779 km²,
 190 respectively. The Ocreza River basin is characterised by a Mediterranean climate with mean
 191 annual precipitation of ≈893 mm and a mean annual discharge at the study site of ≈10.2 m³s⁻
 192 ¹. Ocreza River is characterised by a pluvial winter flow regime type [38].

193

194 **Fig. 1.** Location of the planned hydropower plant at Ocreza River, a tributary of the Tagus River. The central
 195 panel shows the study site, where the habitat, hydraulic and hydrological data were obtained, and the key
 196 components of the hydropower plant: intake weir, headrace, impacted river reach ≈4 km long, and
 197 powerhouse. Two left panels show respectively, the hydrographic network (upper) and the study site
 198 watershed location in the Tagus River basin (lower). The hydromorphological configuration of the study site is
 199 shown in Fig. 2.

200

201 The wet period begins in the middle of Autumn (i.e., November) and lasts until early Spring
 202 (i.e., April), (see, Fig. A1). Summer (i.e., July, August, and September) is the driest season
 203 with a mean discharge of ≈0.25 m³s⁻¹ and also characterised by several days of null flows. As
 204 found by [Kuriqi, Pinheiro \[36\]](#) and [Bejarano, Sordo-Ward \[27\]](#), pluvial winter flow regime
 205 rivers are considered to be suitable for the development of RoR hydropower plants.
 206 Although several hydropower projects have been proposed in Ocreza River, (i.e., as can be
 207 seen from Google Earth images, there have already been initiated some excavation works at
 208 the site selected for this study), the river is still undisturbed in its entire length. The study
 209 site includes a river reach of 500-m long, where the river flows freely through the coarse

210 substrate, dominated mainly by boulders. In terms of hydromorphological configuration [39,
 211 40], the study site is characterised by quite diverse Hydromorphological Units (HMUs).
 212 Detailed information about the hydromorphological characterisation of the study site is
 213 given in Fig. 2.

214 **Fig. 2.** Closer view of the study site. Upper panels, from left to right show respectively, river bed elevation,
 215 water depth including HMUs, (i.e., 1) pool; 2) run; 3) riffle; 4) slackwater; and 5) habitat general) and flow
 216 velocity for optimum discharge $Q \approx 25 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ which correspond to the highest habitat availability. The lower
 217 panel shows the longitudinal profile and Water Surface Level (W.S. Level) of the study site for the same
 218 discharge. Detailed information about the HMUs features and ecological functions is given in Table 1.
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221 The types of HMUs that characterise the study site represent all types of HMUs
 222 characterising the impacted river reach. Five HMUs, such as pool, run, riffle, slackwater, and
 223 habitat general, were identified. Specific geomorphological and hydraulic features
 224 characterise each of the HMUs (Table 1). Notably, the first four HMUs have an essential role
 225 in the proper functioning of the aquatic biota [41]. Aquatic biota, in terms of the fish
 226 community, is composed mainly of native cyprinid species such as *Pseudochondrostoma*
 227 *polylepis* (Iberian straight-mouth nase), *Squalius alburnoides* (calandino), and *Luciobarbus*
 228 *bocagei* (Iberian barbel, hereafter barbel) [42]. In this study, we considered only the barbel
 229 as it is the most common and also a near-threatened cyprinid species, particularly in the
 230 South-Western part of the Iberian Peninsula [43].

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Table 1 Brief description of the HMUs-hydromorphological units features, characterising the study site.

HMUs	Hydrogeomorphological Characteristics	Ecological Functions
(1) Pool	Deep-water impoundment formed as a result of natural topographic depression, hydraulic processes, or different channel obstructions; characterised by slow-moving water, low to moderate turbulence, large eddies, and composed mainly by fine sediments deposition.	It provides refuge to fishes and other aquatic fauna from terrestrial predators, enhancing ecosystem resilience due to the hydrological alteration (i.e., floods, droughts, and anthropogenic activities) — spawning and nesting habitat.
(2) Run	Monotone instream channel configuration, laterally concave shape, includes channels areas with fast-moving water, moderate depth, and nonstationary mixed sediment transport/deposition, composed mainly by a coarse substrate.	Spawning, nursery, and feeding areas; suitable mainly for adults and bottom-living fish species; it provides protection from terrestrial predators.
(3) Riffle	Shallow water impoundment, characterised by a moderate gradient and turbulence; low to moderate water velocities, longitudinally flat and laterally convex-streambed shape, coarse substrate, and presence of aquatic vegetation.	High dissolved oxygen concentration, rich in nutrients; rocky bottom provides shelter and protection from predators — suitable for gravel nest spawners.
(4) Slackwater	Off-channel areas near to stream margins, founded in forms of small disconnected pools or backwaters areas; characterised by slow-moving water and great depths.	It provides temporary shelter mainly for fishes; suitable resting and spawning areas; provides rapid biota colonisation, evasion—escape from predators.
(5) Habitat General	Habitat zones that may include wide ranges of areas within the channel, such as boulders, backwaters, inundated mainly during bankfull discharge, very often remaining entirely dewatered, characterised by low dissolved oxygen content and highly fluctuating temperatures.	It does not provide any essential ecological function. Nonetheless, specifically, backwater areas may serve as a temporary refuge for stranded fishes or other aquatic fauna during rapid water level fluctuations.

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236 **2.2 Methodological approach**

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238 The flowchart (Fig. 3) outlines the main components of the methodology developed and
 239 applied in this study, which includes five main steps. The first step consists of the data
 240 acquisition: streamflow and habitat data, respectively. In the second step, potential
 241 hydropower production and e-flow releases considering technical and ecological constraints
 242 were computed on a daily time-scale. The technical constraints are related to the type of
 243 turbine considered in the analysis and its mechanical features [44]. Ecological constraints
 244 include nine scenarios of e-flow releases based on nine hydrological-based EFMs. The third
 245 step involves potential energy production, and e-flow releases characterisation regarding
 246 the influence of nine EFMs.

247
248 **Fig. 3.** The flowchart describes the methodological approach applied in this study.

249
250 In addition, the third step also involves flow regime alteration (hydrologic alteration)
251 analysis following the “*Indicators of Hydrologic Alteration—IHA*” approach [29]. The fourth
252 step consists of the hydraulic and fish habitat simulation considering several data inputs.

253 Finally, in the fifth step, the main outputs from the previous steps, namely energy
254 production, flow regime alteration, and habitat availability are plotted against each other
255 in order to propose possible trade-offs, where hydropower production maximisation would go
256 with less flow regime alteration and provide suitable fish habitat conditions.

257
258 **2.3 Hydrological and habitat data**

259 Historical streamflow data records were obtained from the Portuguese National Water
260 Resources Information System—SNIRH (<https://snirh.apambiente.pt>), at a gauging station
261 near to the study site. The observed streamflow series considered in this study span over 33
262 years (1984-2017) of mean daily flow data. The dataset includes only full years of
263 observation; sparse missing data have been linearly interpolated. The length and the quality
264 of the dataset were chosen under the recommendation of [Richter, Baumgartner \[29\]](#). The
265 habitat data consist on: detailed topography of the river reach where several hydraulic

266 parameters were measured regarding specific flow condition, type of roughness, i.e.,
 267 substrate, cover, and vegetation type, and Habitat Suitability Curves—HSCs, i.e., water
 268 velocity, depth and cover preferences for the three life-stages of target fish species [42, 45].
 269 The habitat data were obtained and made freely available by [Rivaes, Boavida \[42\]](#). All
 270 protocols and procedures of the data acquisition on the site are explained in detail in the
 271 reference. [Rivaes, Boavida \[42\]](#) analysed two study sites and three fish species in their paper.
 272 In our study, we used only the habitat data obtained from the study site called “OCBA”, and
 273 we considered only barbel fish, including three life-stages.

274

275 **2.4 Environmental flow methods**

276 The nine EFMs applied in this study are the most commonly recommended and worldwide
 277 applied hydrologically-based methods for e-flows setting at RoR hydropower plants [28, 46].
 278 The applied methods involve different categories of hydrologically-based EFMs, namely:

279 **Annual minimum**, represented by exceedance percentiles of flow duration curve: Q_{75}
 280 (EFM1), Q_{95} (EFM2) respectively; One-third of the Average Summer Flow: 1/3ASF (EFM3); %
 281 of Mean Annual Flow, 5%MAF (EFM4), 10%MAF (EFM5), and 25%MAF (EFM6). Except for
 282 EFM4, the other EFMs were used and are explained in detail in the studies of [Kuriqi, Pinheiro](#)
 283 [\[26\]](#), and [Kuriqi, Pinheiro \[36\]](#). In addition, we decided to test the EFM4, considering the
 284 findings of [Wolter and Schomaker \[47\]](#). They concluded that EFM4 enables the full
 285 functioning of the fish passes at more than 90% of the analysed study cases across Europe.

286 **Monthly minimum**, represented by the Tessmann method (EFM7), which is based on the
 287 division of the year in 12 monthly periods. According to Tessman, the minimum monthly e-
 288 flows (Q_{mfr}) were assigned as a ratio of Mean Monthly Flow (MMF) to MAF, following three
 289 categories [48], Eqs. 1-3:

$$290 \quad \text{If } MMF < 0.4MAF, \text{ then } Q_{mfr}(t) = MMF \quad (1)$$

$$291 \quad \text{If } MMF > 0.4MAF, \text{ and } 0.4MMF < 0.4MAF, \text{ then } Q_{mfr}(t) = 0.4MAF \quad (2)$$

$$292 \quad \text{If } 0.4MMF > 0.4MAF, \text{ then } Q_{mfr}(t) = 0.4MMF \quad (3)$$

293 **Combined**, in order to not only ensure longitudinal connectivity but also to maximise fish
 294 habitat condition by mimicking the Natural Flow Regime (NFR) and enhance spatial
 295 transferability of e-flows implementation, we proposed a combination of annual minimum
 296 with the daily minimum, respectively, 5%MAF+10% Q_{mean} -Daily (EFM8). It should be noted
 297 that this approach could be applied only if the available flow to be allocated as e-flows is
 298 >5%MAF.

299 **Daily minimum**, so-called proportional or dynamic approach represented by 20% Q_{mean} -
 300 Daily (EFM9), assigned e-flows according to this method, corresponding to 20% of mean daily
 301 flow based on historical records of interannual mean daily flow time series [26].

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304 2.5 Hydropower production and environmental flows estimation

305 To cope with the flow variability, which characterises the flow regime type of the Ocreza
 306 river, two Francis turbines with different design discharges were considered. Potential
 307 hydropower production was computed at a daily time step, taking into account ecological
 308 restrictions imposed by the applied EFMs and turbine technical limitations. E-flow was
 309 subtracted from natural flow to obtain available flow. Turbines sizes were chosen to fully
 310 cover the range of available flow from the minimum turbine flow of the smaller one to the
 311 sum of the maximum flows of both turbines. Available flows less than the minimum or more
 312 than maximum turbine flow were spilled. The hydropower production is proportional to the
 313 product of the available river flow discharge and the hydraulic head, and its feasibility is
 314 significantly affected by the later one. Considering the topographical features of the study
 315 site and the economic recommendation about the headrace length [49], the hydraulic head
 316 was assumed to be 41 m. The installed capacity, P , in megawatt (MW) of the hydropower
 317 plant was computed using, Eq.4:

$$318 \quad P(t) = \frac{1}{10^6} \eta_{t_j} \gamma H_{net} Q_{d_j} \quad (4)$$

319 where η_{t_j} is the turbine j efficiency (%), which depends on the turbine type [44], and also
 320 it varies as a function of turbine inflow and design discharge; η_{t_j} was estimated based on the
 321 empirical expression developed by Voros, Kiranoudis [50], $\gamma \approx 9.81$ is the specific weight of
 322 water (kNm^{-3}), H_{net} is the net head (m), and Q_{d_j} is the design discharge for the turbine j (m^3s^{-1}).
 323 In this study, for computation simplicity, H_{net} was assumed constant and equal to the
 324 gross head ($H_g = 41$ m), neglecting the head losses. The total energy production, E , in
 325 gigawatt-hours (GWh) that a turbine j produces over a given time period Δt (days) was
 326 computed using, Eq. 5:

$$327 \quad E(t) = \frac{\tau_h}{10^9} \gamma H_{net} \eta_g \eta_{el} \sum_{t=1}^{t+\Delta t=d_y} (q_{d_j}(t) [\eta_{t_j} \{q_{d_j}(t), Q_{d_j}\}]) \quad (5)$$

328 where τ_h is the number of operating hours per day (24 h); q_{d_j} is the mean daily turbine flow
 329 for the j^{th} turbine (m^3s^{-1}); η_g and η_{el} are generator and electrical efficiencies respectively (%),
 330 assumed to be both constant, whose product is $\approx 90\%$, and finally d_y : represents the number
 331 of days (365 per year). As mentioned above, the hydropower production is constrained by a
 332 minimum (Q_{tech}) and maximum (Q_{d_j}) operating discharges, and e-flow releases. In this
 333 study, Q_{d_j} was assumed to be $10 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ for the larger turbine and $3.5 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ for the smaller
 334 one, Q_{tech} is defined by the producer in order to provide the highest possible efficient
 335 utilisation, and it depends on the type of turbine [44]. Accordingly, there is no hydropower
 336 production if the natural flow discharge is lower than the minimum e-flows resulting from a
 337 given EFM plus the minimum turbine flow. Consequently, considering the minimum e-flows
 338 (Q_{mfr}), released downstream of the diversion structure, the turbine inflow was calculated
 339 following, Eq. 6:

$$340 \quad q_d(t) = [Q_{hydro}(t) - Q_{mfr}(t)] \quad \text{where} \quad Q_{tech} \leq Q_{hydro} \leq Q_{d_j} \quad (6)$$

341 The e-flow releases (Q_{env}) comprise the minimum e-flows (Q_{mfr}) imposed by EFMs and
342 the excess flow discharge over the diversion structure. Thus, the total e-flow releases and
343 hydropower production were estimated according to the following decision rules, Eqs. 7-10:

344
$$\text{If } Q_{nfr}(t) \leq Q_{mfr}(t), \text{ then } Q_{env}(t) = Q_{nfr}(t) \quad (7)$$

345
$$\text{If } Q_{tech} \leq Q_{hydro}(t) \leq Q_{dj}, \text{ then } Q_{env}(t) = Q_{mfr}(t) \quad (8)$$

346
$$\text{If } Q_{hydro}(t) > Q_{dj}, \text{ then } Q_{env}(t) = [Q_{hydro}(t) - Q_{dj}] + Q_{mfr}(t) \quad (9)$$

347
$$\text{If } Q_{hydro}(t) < Q_{tech}, \text{ then } Q_{env}(t) = [Q_{hydro}(t) + Q_{mfr}(t)] = Q_{nfr}(t) \quad (10)$$

348 where Q_{nfr} (m^3s^{-1}) is the natural flow regime before water diversion, and Q_{hydro} (m^3s^{-1}) is
349 the available flow for energy production. Both e-flows and hydropower production
350 variability were characterised over year seasons, considering the interannual mean daily
351 flow time series.

352

353 **2.6 Hydrodynamic and habitat modelling**

354

355 The habitat availability and suitability were evaluated for three life-stages and over four
356 seasons. To do this, first, the hydraulic computations were conducted in order to obtain
357 ecological meaningful hydraulic variables. Then, habitat simulations were performed
358 considering the preference curves for three life-stages of fish and the hydraulic variables.
359 Sections below describe in details all procedures from hydraulic computations to the fish
360 habitat characterisations.

361

362 **2.6.1 Hydrodynamic modelling**

363 The 2D hydraulic simulations were conducted using River2D V.095a model, in an
364 approximately 500-m long river reach of the Ocreza River. River2D is a widely applied
365 software, mainly for fish habitat modelling. [Lee, Kil \[51\]](#) applied River2D to evaluate several
366 enhancement fish habitat quality measures in the urban streams. [Boavida, Caetano \[52\]](#)
367 applied the River2D model to implement e-flows regime measures to mitigate hydropeaking
368 impacts in a Mediterranean river. [Nones \[53\]](#) found that River2D could provide robust results
369 in eco-environmental diversity characterisation of an Alpine river subjected to highly variable
370 flow regime. Overall, River2D is capable of performing simulations both: in steady-state and
371 transient conditions. In general, 2D hydraulic models are superior compared to
372 unidimensional models, especially in terms of spatial characterisation of the hydrodynamic
373 properties [\[54, 55\]](#).

374 River2D, compared to other 2D-hydraulic models, has the advantage of having incorporated
375 the habitat module, among others. The habitat module computes available physical habitat
376 potentially accessible by fishes and/or other aquatic fauna. The topographic data editing and
377 interpolation were conducted in the R2D_Bed module. The purpose of the R2D_Bed module
378 is to annotate and process the bathymetric data. The hydraulic model was already calibrated

379 by [Rivaes, Boavida \[42\]](#). The calibration process consists of the iterative adjustment of the
 380 river bed roughness until a reasonable agreement between observed and simulated water
 381 elevations and velocity profiles at investigated cross-sections are reached [\[42\]](#). The
 382 calibrated model was then introduced in the R2D_Mesh. The purpose of the R2D_Mesh is to
 383 create the finite element mesh and define hydraulic boundary conditions [\[54\]](#). The
 384 computational mesh generated for the river reach is composed of 7,737 elements and
 385 47,847 nodes, with 1 m spatial resolution to capture small spatial scale velocity variation,
 386 following the methodology proposed by [Guedes, Silva \[55\]](#), and [Boavida, Santos \[56\]](#). As
 387 required by the hydrodynamic module of the River2D, the hydraulic boundary conditions
 388 were defined considering the inflow discharge and estimated water surface elevation and
 389 outflow water surface elevation obtained from the rating curve.

390 The river reach understudy is quasi-confined; therefore, the lateral boundary conditions
 391 were set as without runoff. The calibrated model was then used to perform steady-state
 392 simulations in the hydrodynamic module of River2D, considering different flow discharge
 393 ranges from $0.01 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ to $420 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$. The flow discharge ranges used in the hydraulic
 394 simulations were obtained from rating curve and cover all types of flow discharge
 395 magnitudes characterising the interannual mean daily flow discharges. The River2D model
 396 solves two-dimensional depth-averaged St. Venant equations representing the water mass
 397 and two components of the momentum conservation using the finite element method. Two-
 398 dimensional depth-averaged hydrodynamic equations include the bottom friction and
 399 turbulence in longitudinal and lateral directions as follows, [Eqs. 11-13](#):

400 Mass conservation equation:

$$401 \quad \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial q_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial q_y}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (11)$$

402 Momentum conservation equations:

$$403 \quad \frac{\partial q_x}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(Uq_x) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(Vq_x) + \frac{g}{2} \frac{\partial H^2}{\partial x} = gH(S_{0x} - S_{fx}) + \frac{1}{\rho} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(H\tau_{xx}) \right\} + \frac{1}{\rho} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(H\tau_{xy}) \right\} \quad (12)$$

404

$$405 \quad \frac{\partial q_y}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(Uq_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(Vq_y) + \frac{g}{2} \frac{\partial H^2}{\partial x} = gH(S_{0x} - S_{fy}) + \frac{1}{\rho} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(H\tau_{yx}) \right\} + \frac{1}{\rho} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(H\tau_{yy}) \right\} \quad (13)$$

406 where H is the water depth (m), t is time (s); x and y represent stream-wise and transverse
 407 flow directions; U and V are the depth-averaged velocities according to x – and
 408 y – directions (ms^{-1}); $q_x [= HU]$ and $q_y [= HV]$ represent the unit discharges in the x – and
 409 y – directions (m^3s^{-1}); S_{0i} and S_{fi} are the friction slopes in the x – and y – directions (m/m);
 410 g is the gravitational acceleration (ms^{-2}); ρ is the water density (kgm^{-3}); and τ_{ij} represent the
 411 shear stress forces (Pa). The friction slope, according to x and y directions were computed
 412 following, [Eqs.14 and 15](#):

$$413 \quad S_{fx} = \frac{n^2 U \sqrt{U^2 + V^2}}{H^{4/3}} \quad (14)$$

$$414 \quad S_{fy} = \frac{n^2 V \sqrt{U^2 + V^2}}{H^{4/3}} \quad (15)$$

415 where n is the Manning's roughness coefficient. Finally, the main outputs obtained from
 416 2D hydraulic simulations, which serve as inputs for the habitat modelling, were: water depth
 417 and flow velocity at every single cell of the river mesh related to each flow discharge
 418 considered in the hydraulic simulations.

419

420 2.6.2 Habitat modelling

421 The habitat module of the River2D model is based on the Weighted Usable Area—WUA
 422 approach, proposed by Bovee [45]. The WUA reflects the quantity of available physical
 423 habitat as surface area (m^2), which can potentially be used by a specific fish species at a
 424 particular life-stage [56]. The habitat component of the River2D integrates hydraulic
 425 variables, i.e., water depth and flow velocity with over year seasons HSCs [42]. HSCs contain
 426 observed biological preferences data for substrate, depth, velocity, and cover. Barbel has
 427 demonstrated similar preferences for Autumn and Winter, whereas different preferences
 428 were observed for other seasons (Fig. A2). The capability of the River2D to include the
 429 substrate and cover concurrently allows computing Composite Suitability Index (CSI) values,
 430 ranging between 0 and 1, which represent the most unsuitable and optimal habitat
 431 conditions, respectively (Table 2), [54, 57].

432

Table 2 Categories of fish habitat suitability.

Class	CSI Range	Habitat suitability degree
I	$0.3 > CSI > 0$	Poor
II	$0.6 > CSI > 0.3$	Intermediate
III	$0.8 > CSI > 0.6$	Good
IV	$1.0 > CSI > 0.8$	Optimal

433

434 Thus, the preference indices of depth (Depth Suitability Index—DSI), velocity (Velocity
 435 Suitability Index—VSI), Channel Suitability Index related substrate— Ci_sSI , and Channel
 436 Suitability Index related cover— Ci_cSI were multiplied to provide Composed Suitability Index
 437 (CSI_{sc}) [45], Eqs. 16-18:

$$438 \quad CI_s = VSI \times DSI \times Ci_sSI \quad (16)$$

$$439 \quad CI_c = VSI \times DSI \times Ci_cSI \quad (17)$$

$$440 \quad CSI_{sc} = VSI \times DSI \times \sqrt{Ci_sSI \times Ci_cSI} \quad (18)$$

441 The WUA then was computed by multiplying each of three CSI_i by the contributing area
 442 surrounding each cell, Eq. 19:

$$443 \quad WUA f(Q, T) = \sum_{i=1}^N CSI_i \times A_i \quad (19)$$

444 where N represents the number of cells and A_i is the area of the i^{th} cell (m^2). Finally, WUA
 445 was initially computed considering flow discharge ranges used in the hydraulic simulations
 446 for three life-stages of the barbel fish (i.e., juvenile, small adults, and adults) at four seasons
 447 based on seasonal HSCs. The WUA exhibit a non-linear relationship with flow discharge.
 448 Thus, higher flow discharge did not necessarily provide higher WUA. The WUA values

449 increase up to a specific value of flow discharge, which in this study corresponds to $Q \approx 25$
450 m^3s^{-1} , then decreases as the discharge increases from 25 to 420 m^3s^{-1} .

451

452 **2.7 Flow regime alteration and habitat availability characterisation**

453 The well-recognised “Indicator of Hydrologic of Alteration (IHA)” method was applied to
454 characterise the flow regime alteration due to hydropower production imposed by nine
455 hydrologically-based EFMs [29]. The IHA methodology comprises a set of ecologically
456 meaningful hydrologic indices, namely 33 IHA parameters and 34 E-flow Component (EFC)
457 parameters sorted into five groups. For simplicity of analysis, we characterised the flow
458 alteration employing five global indices derived from IHA, proposed by [Kuriqi, Pinheiro \[26\]](#),
459 namely: Mean Monthly flow alteration Index (I_{MM}), Magnitude and Duration of Extreme flow
460 alteration Index (I_{MDE}), Timing of Extreme flow alteration Index (I_{TE}), Frequency and Duration
461 alteration Index (I_{FD}), and Rate and Frequency alteration Index (I_{RF}); computed as follows,
462 [Eq.20](#):

$$463 \quad I_{i,j} (HI_{i,j}) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{HI_{i,j}nfr - HI_{i,j}afr}{HI_{i,j}nfr} \right| \right) \left(\frac{1}{\#HI_{i,j}} \right) \quad (20)$$

464 where $I_{i,j}$ is the alteration index regarding to hydrological indicators i for each group j ,
465 $HI_{i,j}nfr$ is the hydrological Indicator related to the natural flow regime, $HI_{i,j}afr$ is the
466 hydrological Indicator related to the altered flow regime, and $\#HI_{i,j}$ represent the number
467 of hydrological indicators for each group. The five indices were scaled from 0-1 and
468 characterise the flow alteration into four categories: low (0-0.25), mild (0.25-0.5), moderate
469 (0.5-0.75), and high alteration (0.75-1). The alteration of the EFC parameters was calculated
470 as the relative change to the NFR.

471 The habitat availability was characterised in terms of WUA. The discharge values in the time
472 series of mean daily flows were interpolated in the table of WUA obtained from steady flow
473 hydraulic simulations for three life-stages of fish regarding the seasonal HSCs, to generate a
474 time series of mean daily WUA. Time series of mean daily WUA were generated for natural
475 and altered flow regime imposed by nine EFMs. Afterwards, mean daily WUA variability
476 characterisation regarding each life-stage, for natural and altered flow regime was done at a
477 seasonal scale.

478 A threshold of 80% of the maximum WUA (WUA_{max}) for each life-stage, was considered as
479 a boundary for optimal conditions [58]. Moreover, a threshold of 50% of the WUA_{max} for
480 each life-stage was set as a boundary that provides average habitat conditions; below this
481 limit, the habitat conditions become less suitable. The time duration that provided a WUA
482 < 50 and 80% WUA_{max} ; as a result, e-flows restrictions imposed by nine EFMs was computed
483 for each life-stage of fish at four seasons based on the mean daily time series of WUA. Finally,
484 spatial analysis of habitat suitability degree with regards to HMUs that characterise the river
485 reach was assessed in terms of CSI. In this regard, the habitat suitability for natural and
486 altered conditions imposed by nine EFMs was computed considering mean flow values for
487 the most critical season and fish life-stage.

489 **2.8 Multivariate analysis**

490 In this study, we conducted a multivariate analysis in order to assess how different
 491 conflicting objectives, such as the flow regime alteration, hydropower production and fish
 492 habitat availability, were related against each other under the implementation of nine EFMs.
 493 The goal of this analysis was to identify those EFMs that could sustain reasonable
 494 hydropower production while causing less alteration of natural flow regime, which in turns
 495 provides adequate habitat conditions for the well-being of the target fish. Thus, we
 496 recommend that decision on picking the most suitable EFM should be made based on the
 497 aim to achieve a specific objective, e.g., preserving certain hydrologic parameters such as
 498 timing, frequency, duration or to ensure habitat availability above specific thresholds at least
 499 for the most critical period of the target fish life cycle while guaranteeing feasible
 500 hydropower operation. For clarity and simplicity, the analysis was conducted considering
 501 three primary objective functions, namely: hydropower production maximisation—*Obj1*,
 502 (Eq.21), minimisation of flow regime alteration—*Obj2*, (Eq.22), and maximisation of WUA—
 503 *Obj3*, (Eq.23). *Obj1* is formulated as mean annual energy production, *Obj2* is expressed in
 504 terms of five global indices, and *Obj3* is given as % of mean WUA deviation from natural
 505 habitat conditions (WUA_D).

$$506 \quad Obj1 = \left\{ E = \frac{\tau_h}{10^9} \gamma H_{net} \eta_G \sum_{t=1}^{t+\Delta t=d_y} q_d(t) \eta_{T_j} \right\} \quad (21)$$

$$507 \quad Obj2 = \left\{ I_{i,j} (HI_{i,j}) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{HI_{i,j}^{nfr} - HI_{i,j}^{afr}}{HI_{i,j}^{nfr}} \right| \right) \left(\frac{1}{\#HI_{i,j}} \right) \right\} \quad (22)$$

$$508 \quad Obj3 = \left\{ \overline{WUA}_D = \left[\left(\frac{\overline{WUA}_A}{\overline{WUA}_N} \right) - 1 \right] \times 100\% \right\} \quad (23)$$

509 where \overline{WUA}_D is the mean WUA deviation (%), \overline{WUA}_A is the mean WUA for altered habitat
 510 conditions (m^2), and \overline{WUA}_N is the mean WUA for natural habitat conditions (m^2). It was
 511 found that during a specific period of the year and for certain life-stage of the target fish,
 512 natural flow discharge reduction me lead to increase of WUA. Therefore, from the Eq. 23, if
 513 the \overline{WUA}_D was positive then we have habitat gain, whereas if the \overline{WUA}_D was negative then
 514 we have habitat loss. Thus, with the above formulations, we compare the results of applying
 515 different EFMs and determine which of them could provide good trade-off among these
 516 three objective functions. The mathematical-based optimisation is out of the scope of this
 517 study.

518

519 **2.9 Study limitations**

520 Very often, the diversion structure at such hydropower scheme may create small storage
 521 that provides short-term regulation (i.e., hourly or daily) allowing for adjustment to the
 522 electricity demand, depending on the storage size. In this study, the hydropower plant
 523 operation model was simplified. The only decision was to turbine or not to turbine, based
 524 only on flow availability. Thus, the hydropower plant is considered to be operating only if the

525 natural flow discharge is higher than the minimum e-flows resulting from a given EFM plus
526 the minimum turbine flow.

527 Also, it was assumed that the maintenance period accord with low flow periods when flow
528 availability does not meet minimum technical flow. Nevertheless, this assumption cannot
529 always be reached in practice because of several reasons such as the absence of low-flow
530 periods at any given year to carry out full maintenance of the facility, or depending on the
531 flow regime the maintenance operation may be scheduled during high flows only. Moreover,
532 the assumption of two turbines may not always stand, since depending on the business plan,
533 some hydropower plants may be equipped with only one turbine, two of the same size, or
534 more than two.

535 For simplicity, it was assumed that both turbines work under the constant head, neglecting
536 the hydraulic losses. However, in practice, turbines are exposed to variable head, and
537 efficiency varies for the range of possible flow-head situations. Finally, it was assumed that
538 all energy production from the hydropower plant would be transmitted to the energy
539 network regardless of fluctuations in energy demand or the production of other
540 renewable/non-renewable sources.

541 There are also some limitations concerning the ecohydraulic part of the study since it was
542 assumed that river geomorphology does not significantly change. However, during specific
543 periods, particularly during high flow periods, the river bathymetry may change. Another
544 limitation is related to the precise determination of the fish species/life-stages to be
545 considered in the e-flows regime [55]. WUA-based fish habitat assessment approach consists
546 solely of the quantity of the habitat neglecting the long-term habitat quality, such as
547 fragmentation, connectivity between HMUs, and water quality deterioration due to water
548 abstraction [54]. Although these simplifications may be significant for specific cases;
549 nevertheless, considering the objectives of this study, they have a limited effect on the main
550 findings and conclusions. Moreover, RoR hydropower plants without regulation, operate
551 under limited degrees of freedom; therefore, the assumptions considered in this study are
552 rational.

553

554 **3 Results**

555 In this section are presented the main findings concerning the hydropower production, e-
556 flows, flow regime alteration, and impacts on fish habitat. Respectively, [Section 3.1](#) present
557 seasonal variation of hydropower production and e-flow releases. Flow regime alteration
558 regarding applied EFMs is described in [Section 3.2](#). Impacts on fish habitat over seasons and
559 three life-stages are presented in [Section 3.3](#). Finally, [Section 3.4](#) shows how flow regime
560 alteration, hydropower production, and habitat loss are related to each other.

561

3.1 Seasonal hydropower production and environmental flow releases characterisation

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Interannual hydropower production (Fig. 4) and e-flow releases (Fig.5) show notable differences among EFMs and seasons as well. In general, all EFMs show significantly high variability in the hydropower production during all seasons except for the Winter. The reason for high variability is first directly linked to the variability of flow discharge and secondly due to the resections imposed by the EFMs. Hydropower production is more sensitive to such restriction, notably during low flow periods.

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Fig. 4. Notched boxplots and density plots (i.e., vertical curved plots) show the interannual energy production regarding nine EFMs at the seasonal scale. The dotted line shows the mean interannual energy production at the seasonal scale regarding each EFM.

575 The three first EFMs follow quite a similar trend regarding the hydropower production
576 during Autumn, Winter and Spring seasons. Also, EFM8 and EFM9 allow for similar
577 hydropower production, but only during Winter season. Whereas during the Summer
578 season, all EFMs, distinctly provide quite different hydropower production. Further, results
579 show that EFM2 allows for the highest hydropower production during all seasons. At the
580 same time, EFM7 imposes relatively high restriction by providing the lowest hydropower
581 production at all seasons, excluding Summer, when the EFM6 imposes the lowest
582 hydropower production. On the other side, concerning the e-flow releases (Fig.5), on the
583 contrary to the hydropower production, EFMs show high variability during Autumn, Winter
584 and Spring seasons and low variability during Summer season. In terms of ecosystem needs,
585 the high variability of flow regime is positive as it drives several geomorphological and

586 biological processes. Low variability of e-flow releases notably during Summer indicates high
 587 competition with hydropower production. Moreover, it shows that e-flows are close to the
 588 minimum discharges provided by each EFM; there are no, or only a few surpluses spill over
 589 the weir during the Summer season.

590

Methods

591 **Fig. 5.** Notched boxplots and density plots (i.e., vertical curved plots) show the interannual e-flow releases
 592 regarding nine EFMs at the seasonal scale. The dotted line shows the mean interannual e-flow releases at the
 593 seasonal scale regarding each EFM.

594

Methods

595 Results show that e-flow releases imposed by nine EFMs were significantly lower than NFR,
 596 during the four seasons, particularly during Winter, Spring, and Summer the differences were
 597 notably higher than during the other seasons. However, during the Autumn and Winter
 598 seasons, all EFMs provide quite similar e-flows among them, except EFM7, which enables
 599 slightly higher e-flow releases. Nevertheless, minimum e-flow releases imposed by each
 600 EFM, during Winter remain higher than other seasons. During Spring season, the three first
 601 and two last EFMs provide quite similar e-flows; the rest produce significantly different e-
 602 flow releases among them. Finally, during the Summer season, differences among EMFs and
 603 between NFR and e-flows imposed by each EFM were significantly higher than during the
 604 other seasons. During Summer, contrary to the other seasons, EFM6 produces the highest
 605 e-flow releases, whereas EFM2 produces the lowest. Overall, in terms of hydropower
 606 production, EFM2 allows for the highest hydropower production throughout the year. On
 607 the other side, EFM7, except for Summer season, enables the highest e-flow releases during
 608 all three other seasons.

609

610 **3.2 Flow regime alteration**

611 River flow diversion due to hydropower production altered natural flow regime. Results
 612 (Fig.5) show that some of the EFM's cause substantial alteration of the natural flow regime,
 613 which consequently may lead to several ecological impacts in the riverine ecosystem, see
 614 Table A1 for the alteration degree of each Indicator imposed by the EFM's. Nevertheless, five
 615 global indices show that the degree of alteration differs among EFM's (Fig.6).

616 Namely, EM2 imposes moderate Mean Monthly flow alteration Index (I_{MM}), whereas the
 617 other EFM's except for EFM6 show mild I_{MM} . Regarding Magnitude and Duration of Extreme
 618 flow alteration Index (I_{MDE}), EFM1-EFM3 and EFM9 show mild alteration, the rest of EFM's
 619 impose low I_{MDE} . Concerning the Timing of Extreme flow alteration Index (I_{TE}), almost all
 620 EFM's show insignificant alteration, except for EFM2 which cause slightly higher I_{TE} than the
 621 other EFM's. EFM2 and EFM9 impose mild Frequency and Duration alteration Index (I_{FD}),
 622 whereas the rest of EFM's causes low I_{FD} . Finally, as revealed through the Rate and Frequency
 623 alteration Index (I_{RF}), three first EFM's impose mild alteration with regards to frequency and
 624 rate of change, the rest of the EFM's show low I_{RF} .

625 **Fig. 6.** Overlaid bars with the same origin show flow regime alteration presented as mean values of five global
 626 indices regarding nine EFM's. The five indices were classified into four categories, low (0-0.25), mild (0.25-0.5),
 627 moderate (0.5-0.75), and high alteration (0.75-1).
 628
 629

630 Overall, EFM2 causes the highest flow alteration, EFM6 the lowest. Looking at the EFC
 631 parameters alteration (Table 3), the results show that mainly the first four EFM's cause a
 632 substantial decrease in low flow variability, refer Table A2 for detail information of each EFC
 633 alteration induced by nine EFM's. The most affected EFC were low flows from December to
 634 May and the high flow related to EFC thresholds. EFM5 and EFM8 impose a mild to a
 635 moderate decrease of the variability, while EFM6, EFM7 and particularly EFM9 cause a
 636 significantly lower decrease of the flow variability. Concerning the alteration of the EFC, with
 637 regards to the increase of variability, results show that almost all EFM's have insignificant
 638 influence, except for large floods rise/fall rate where first seven EFM's have considerably
 639 increased variability of those parameters. Overall, EFM6-EFM9 tend to preserve the EFC

640 parameters close to the NFR. These findings suggest that EFM6-EFM9 provide much better
 641 results with regards to the riverine ecosystem conservation.

642

643 **Table 3** Relative change of the EFC regarding nine EFMs against NFR, represented by the coefficient of variation
 644 (Cv). Sign (+) symbolises an increase and (-) a decrease.

EFC	Relative change (%)									
	EFM1	EFM2	EFM3	EFM4	EFM5	EFM6	EFM7	EFM8	EFM9	
EFC Low Flows	Oct Low Flow	-77	-82	-81	-58	-42	-23	-16	-45	-1
	Nov Low Flow	-80	-84	-81	-67	-53	-32	-5	-47	1
	Dec Low Flow	-100	-100	-100	-98	-78	-45	-13	-63	0
	Jan Low Flow	-100	-100	-100	-100	-94	-66	-25	-56	0
	Feb Low Flow	-100	-100	-100	-100	-91	-57	-10	-54	0
	Mar Low Flow	-100	-100	-100	-99	-86	-54	-10	-59	0
	Apr Low Flow	-100	-100	-100	-97	-74	-37	-18	-58	0
	May Low Flow	-99	-99	-99	-78	-52	-22	-7	-54	0
	Jun Low Flow	-83	-86	-87	-54	-37	-15	-25	-45	-1
	Jul Low Flow	-78	-83	-82	-59	-43	-14	-59	-53	-10
	Aug Low Flow	-69	-75	-75	-43	-32	-15	-73	-36	-15
Sep Low Flow	-67	-73	-74	-42	-21	-8	-48	-35	-11	
EFC Parameters	Extreme low peak	36	-79	36	36	36	36	36	36	-19
	Extreme low duration	-29	-64	-29	-29	-29	-29	-29	-29	36
	Extreme low timing	-3	49	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-18
	Extreme low frequency	23	-76	23	23	23	23	23	23	-48
	High flow peak	44	38	42	26	38	7	35	30	30
	High flow duration	9	8	6	7	15	0	67	0	0
	High flow timing	85	61	78	-8	-14	-8	-7	0	0
	High flow frequency	-17	-2	-16	-9	-10	-5	16	0	0
	High flow rise rate	9	6	9	2	18	16	22	20	19
	High flow fall rate	67	42	45	32	51	27	29	54	48
	Small Flood peak	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	4	4
	Small Flood duration	10	6	10	10	9	17	29	0	0
	Small Flood timing	38	38	38	38	38	38	57	0	0
	Small Flood frequency	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-20	0	0
	Small Flood rise rate	-39	-39	-39	-39	-39	-38	1	0	0
	Small Flood fall rate	31	34	31	30	22	31	86	0	0
	Large flood peak	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Large flood duration	-5	-5	-5	-10	-16	-13	95	0	0
	Large flood timing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Large flood frequency	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Large flood rise rate	203	203	203	203	203	203	207	0	0	
Large flood fall rate	43	43	43	58	73	84	29	0	0	
EFC Thresholds	High flow	-98	-100	-99	-92	-84	-62	-28	-82	-80
	Extreme low flow	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Small flood	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5
	Large flood	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3

645

646 **3.3 Habitat availability characterisation**

647 Habitat availability results demonstrated that high discharge did not necessarily provide the
648 optimal condition for the Iberian barbel along the year and regarding three life-stages. The
649 highest habitat availability (WUA) for three life-stages (i.e., juveniles-JV, small adults-SA, and
650 adults-A) was reached during Spring season for $Q \approx 25 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Fig. 7). The curves of WUA versus
651 discharge related to the natural flow regime, show that three life-stages of the Iberian barbel
652 revealed almost the same pattern; there is an increase of WUA by reaching the optimal
653 ecological condition at $Q \approx 25 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and then followed by a monotonous decreasing trend even
654 though flow discharge increase.

655 **Fig. 7.** Variation of WUA versus discharge related to three life-stages of the fish during Spring season. Boxplots
656 show the WUA variability for each life-stage; min and max, median, and 25th, 75th percentiles, respectively.
657

658

659 Seasonal WUA variability characterisation of the habitat availability for three life-stages
660 shows substantial differences among the nine EFMs (Fig. 8). In general, the three fish life-
661 stages demonstrate to be less vulnerable to water diversion during the Autumn and Winter
662 seasons, regardless of the applied EFM. During the Autumn, except for EFM2 for juveniles
663 and small adults, and EFM2 and EFM3 for adults fish, the rest of EFMs provide above-average
664 threshold (i.e., $>50\% \text{ WUA}_{\text{max}}$) habitat conditions; moreover, EFM4-EFM6 and EFM8 provide
665 even higher habitat availability than NFR, for the three life-stages. Winter appears to be less
666 vulnerable than Autumn season; in the case of juvenile fish, except for EFM2 which stands
667 at the limits of average habitat conditions, the rest of EFMs, similar to Autumn season
668 provide above optimal threshold (i.e., $>80\% \text{ WUA}_{\text{max}}$) or even higher habitat availability than
669 NFR. Concerning the small adults and adults, except for EFM2, the rest of EFMs provide over
670 average habitat conditions.

671 It is worth highlighting that three life-stages of fish demonstrate to be more sensitive to
672 water diversion during the Spring than two previous seasons. Indeed, during Spring, the
673 three first EFMs impose below-average habitat conditions. In contrast, the rest of the EFMs
674 provides between average and optimal habitat conditions. Results also show that contrary

675 to previous seasons, during Spring, EFM7 provides the highest habitat availability, including
 676 three life-stages.

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Methods

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Fig. 8. Notched boxplots and density plots (i.e., vertical curved plots) show the interannual WUA variability at the seasonal scale for three life-stages of fish, regarding nine EFMs. The dotted line shows the mean interannual WUA for three life-stages at the seasonal scale, regarding each EFM. Green and the red horizontal lines represent the thresholds; 80% and 50% of WUA_{max} , related to optimal and average habitat conditions respectively.

684 Although during the Summer season, the habitat conditions were expected to be more
 685 deteriorated, results show that only EFM2 and EFM9 impose below-average habitat

686 conditions. In contrast, the other EFM2s provide between average and optimal conditions.
 687 The higher habitat availability provided by some EFM2s, in some cases, is due to non-linear
 688 relationship habitat-flow discharge; as mentioned above higher flow discharge does not
 689 necessarily provide better habitat conditions for all life-stages and along the year. Therefore,
 690 partial diversion of available flow discharge for electricity generation may even improve the
 691 habitat conditions downstream of the diversion during specific periods of the year and for
 692 certain life-stages. Overall, EFM2 induced the highest habitat alteration for all seasons and
 693 the life-stages, in contrast, the other EFM2s show different results among seasons and life-
 694 stages. Habitat conditions imposed by EFM2 were under the defined thresholds (i.e., <80
 695 and 50% of WUA_{max}) almost, all the time (Table 4).

696 **Table 4** Time duration in % of WUA under the thresholds (<80 and 50% of WUA_{max}), for three fish life-stages
 697 and nine EFM2s, over year seasons.

Seasons	WUA Thresholds	Life-Stages	NFR	EFM1	EFM2	EFM3	EFM4	EFM5	EFM6	EFM7	EFM8	EFM9
Autumn	80% WUA _{max}	JV	10	0	100	0	0	0	0	10	0	0
		SA	6	90	100	100	0	0	0	3	0	13
		A	6	100	100	100	0	0	0	0	0	35
	Mean	8	63	100	67	0	0	0	4	0	16	
	50% WUA _{max}	JV	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		SA	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
A		0	0	100	81	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Mean	0	0	100	27	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Winter	80% WUA _{max}	JV	29	0	100	0	0	0	0	29	0	0
		SA	52	0	100	19	0	0	0	23	0	0
		A	42	97	100	100	0	0	0	13	0	0
	Mean	41	32	100	40	0	0	0	22	0	0	
	50% WUA _{max}	JV	0	0	55	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		SA	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
A		0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Mean	0	0	85	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Spring	80 WUA _{max}	JV	13	100	100	100	100	100	61	32	100	100
		SA	13	100	100	100	100	100	65	32	100	100
		A	13	100	100	100	100	100	90	32	100	100
	Mean	13	100	100	100	100	100	72	32	100	100	
	50% WUA _{max}	JV	0	100	100	100	23	0	0	0	0	29
		SA	0	100	100	100	16	0	0	0	0	29
A		0	100	100	100	77	0	0	0	23	97	
Mean	0	100	100	100	39	0	0	0	8	52		
Summer	80% WUA _{max}	JV	35	100	100	100	71	58	52	84	71	100
		SA	13	97	100	100	19	13	13	65	16	100
		A	35	100	100	100	61	42	42	74	55	100
	Mean	28	99	100	100	51	38	35	74	47	100	
	50% WUA _{max}	JV	0	0	100	32	0	0	0	0	0	100
		SA	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	97
A		0	0	100	3	0	0	0	0	0	97	
Mean	0	0	100	12	0	0	0	0	0	98		

698

699 After EFM2; EFM1, EFM3, and EFM8 also imposed remarkably high alteration by reducing
700 the habitat availability below-defined thresholds, namely below optimal conditions most of
701 the time, notably during Spring and Summer seasons. Also, it should be noted the Spring was
702 the most affected season due to the water diversion, except for EFM6 and EFM7, the other
703 EFMs imposed all the time habitat availability below optimal conditions. Nevertheless,
704 EFM5-EFM8 ensured at least average habitat conditions during Spring season when the
705 hydropower was assumed to be in operation. Adults life-stage resulted in being most
706 affected due to the water diversion induced through nine EMFs. Spatial analysis of the
707 habitat suitability (Fig. 9) shows notable differences among HMUs.

708

709 **Fig. 9.** Spatial characterisation of habitat suitability for adults in terms of CSI during the Spring season, regarding
710 each EFM. Refer to Fig. 2 for HMUs composition and Table 1 for specific features and ecological functions of
711 each HMUs type.

712

713 In general, HMUs, such as riffle, slackwater and run, were more vulnerable to the water
714 diversion, regardless of applied EFM. Concerning the influence of EFMs on habitat suitability,
715 results show that the three first EFMs have considerably deteriorated almost at the same
716 degree the habitat suitability, particularly, the upstream part of the river each. Whereas
717 EFM4, EFM8, and EFM9 demonstrate to have a little lower impact compared to three first
718 EFMs. Finally, among nine EFMs, only EFM5-EFM9 could provide better habitat suitability,
719 for all types of HMUs characterising the study site.

720

721 **3.4 Suitability of environmental flow methods regarding hydropower production, flow**
722 **regime alteration, and habitat availability**

723 Multivariate analysis between flow regime alteration represented by five indices, mean
724 habitat availability deviation (\overline{WUA}_D), and mean hydropower production demonstrate
725 notable differences among life-stages of fish and EFMs. Concerning the (\overline{WUA}_D), aggregation
726 of the mean interannual values of WUA showed that overall, there was a loss of the habitat
727 availability (i.e., loss of WUA). Results (Fig. 10) display that for the juvenile life-stage, EFM2,
728 although allowing for the highest hydropower production, concurrently imposes the highest
729 flow regime alteration and habitat loss (over 50%) related to five indices.

730

731

Fig. 10. Relation of flow regime alteration in terms of five global alteration indices, mean hydropower production and mean habitat availability loss in terms of \overline{WUA}_D for each life-stages of fish, regarding nine EFM. Each number in the plots represents an EFM, e.g., 1 stand for EFM1.

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735 Conversely, EFM5-EFM7 impose the lowest flow regime alteration and habitat loss;
736 nevertheless, low alteration at five indices was achieved at a high cost of hydropower
737 production. Regarding small adults, EFM2 and EFM3 enable the highest hydropower
738 production. However, simultaneously, flow regime alteration and habitat losses imposed by
739 these two EFMs were higher than 50% related to five indices. Similar to the juvenile stage,
740 EFM5-EFM7 impose the lowest flow regime alteration and habitat loss regarding five indices,
741 but, in turn, affected the hydropower production considerably. Finally, for the adult's life-
742 stage, EFM1-EFM3 demonstrate to be more rational in terms of hydropower production;
743 nevertheless, they cause the highest flow regime alteration and habitat losses over 50% with
744 regards to five indices. On the contrary of two previous life-stages, in case of adults life-stage,
745 only EFM6 and EFM7 have the lowest impact on flow regime alteration and habitat
746 availability, simultaneously; nevertheless, they impose a higher restriction on hydropower
747 production. Results also demonstrate that low flow regime alteration, e.g., low I_{TE} , did not
748 necessarily comply with low habitat loss. Overall, results show that EFM4, EFM8, and mainly
749 EFM9 could provide consistent results, particularly for small adults and adults life-stages
750 considering the three objectives, (i.e., flow regime alteration, \overline{WUA}_D , and hydropower
751 production) integrally.

752

753 **4 Discussion**

754 This study showed that although there are numerous constraints in achieving a rational
755 agreement between hydropower production and riverine ecosystem conservation, still it is
756 possible that at least during a specific period of the year such agreement can be achieved.
757 Moreover, the adequate e-flows setting is crucial in supporting both hydropower production
758 and riverine ecosystem conservation. This section discusses the main findings resulting from
759 the extensive analyses conducted in this study. [Section 4.1](#) discusses strategies in maximising
760 hydropower production. [Section 4.2](#) discusses the e-flows-based recommendations in the
761 conservation of the riverine ecosystem. Finally, [Section 4.3](#) discusses strategies in running
762 the hydropower sustainably by adequate e-flows implantation and also considering other
763 innovative concepts such as energy mix/ hybridisation.

764

765 **4.1 Hydropower production**

766 Because of the general perception about RoR hydropower as clean energy sources
767 associated with little impact on the environment, planning and management of such
768 schemes very often lack the appropriate measures (e.g., e-flows implementation) for riverine
769 aquatic ecosystem conservation. This study investigates the influence of nine hydrologically-
770 based EFMs on hydropower production and aquatic habitat conditions based on an
771 interdisciplinary approach, which involves hydropower production maximisation and well-
772 being of the aquatic ecosystem. This study offers a new approach and practical insights on

773 small RoR hydropower plants, in the light of sustainable development and fulfilment of
774 energy needs.

775 In contrast to hydropower plants with intra/interannual regulation, where several variables
776 can be considered while maximising the power production, the same approach is not valid
777 for RoR hydropower plant. RoR hydropower production is strongly dependent on real-time
778 flow availability; the later one is sensitive to regime type and the portion of flow released as
779 e-flow. Previous studies on the influence of the hydrologically-based EFMs on the RoR
780 hydropower production show that results are site-specific [37] and strongly affected by flow
781 regime type [27, 36]. Although pluvial winter flow regime attests to be suitable for RoR
782 hydropower plant development in terms of the energy production stability and ecological
783 impacts, still appropriate e-flows setting remains a crucial and challenging task. Thus, the
784 non-adequate e-flows determination may lead to substantial ecological impacts [34].
785 However, it could also compromise the hydropower profitability [26, 37]. Other studies show
786 that seasonality also might affect both hydropower production [59] and the riverine
787 ecosystem [37, 48]. Seasonal analysis of the hydropower production in this study shows that
788 some of the applied EFMs, i.e., particularly EFM2, but EFM3, EFM8, and EFM9 also, allow for
789 the highest hydropower production at all seasons. In this regards, our findings are in line
790 with those of previous studies [36, 37] and [26, 38].

791 Conversely, the other applied EFMs, especially EFM6 and EFM7, but EFM4 and EFM5 as
792 well, reveal to be significantly depended on the season characteristics and fish's life-stage.
793 For instance, EFM6 imposes the lowest hydropower production during Autumn, Winter, and
794 Spring seasons; nevertheless, during Summer, EFM7 is ranked among EFMs that provide the
795 highest hydropower production, the opposite result was observed for EFM6 during the same
796 season. On the one hand, the minimum e-flows imposed by each EFMs, influence the
797 hydropower production at each season, one the other hand, minimum technical operation
798 flow may also affect the EFMs performance at a particular season [31]. In this regard, further
799 research is needed in order to understand possible synchronisation of minimum turbine flow
800 with minimum e-flow releases and also investigating which type of turbines enables such
801 operation at a low cost.

802

803 **4.2 Flow regime and habitat alteration**

804 Although RoR hydropower plants without regulation use only a portion of natural flow
805 discharge, still it may hamper river integrity and conservation not only in the depleted river
806 reach but also upstream of the water intake by altering food availability or habitat
807 heterogeneity because of the connectivity loss [15]. Seasonal e-flow releases estimation,
808 particularly during the Autumn and Winter seasons, show that, contrary to the hydropower
809 production, there were no significant differences among EFMs. Little differences among
810 EFMs could be explained by the wet period, which corresponds to late Autumn and Winter
811 seasons. Nevertheless, high variability in e-flow releases during Autumn and Winter seasons
812 indicate that particularly, low e-flows components might be substantially affected [26, 48].

813 Therefore, results do not necessarily suggest picking the EFMs randomly like it happen very
814 often in practice in case of RoR hydropower plants [11, 28]. Instead, extensive analysis is
815 needed before choosing the right EFM.

816 Nevertheless, our findings did also demonstrate that similar to [Walega, Mlynski \[48\]](#), and
817 [Karakoyun, Yumurtaci \[35\]](#), the Tessmann method (i.e., EFM7) provides the highest e-flow
818 releases most of the time, except for the Summer season. Additionally, EFM7 caused lower
819 flow regime alteration compared to the other applied EFMs. Although hydrologically-based
820 EFMs, remain widely applied, they yield e-flow releases thresholds with no strong ecological
821 foundations that in turn leads to uncertainty at which extent the natural flow regime of a
822 river can be altered. Furthermore, indicators-based flow regime alteration estimation can
823 give a comprehensive overview on the impacts due to the water diversion for the
824 hydropower production; nevertheless, they fail to assess the real impact on the biota, e.g.,
825 fish [28, 60]. Habitat simulation applied in this study provided some crucial insights to better
826 understand the influence and linkage of hydrologically-based EFMs on fish habitat, at
827 different life-stages and seasons. Results demonstrate that water diversion does not always
828 induce habitat loss, and higher e-flow releases did not necessarily guarantee better habitat
829 conditions for the target fish species at specific life-stages. For instance, our findings indicate
830 that higher e-flow releases provided by EFM7 during Autumn and Winter seasons were not
831 positively reflected on the habitat availability. Also, low e-flow releases imposed by some of
832 the EFMs, e.g., EFM1, EFM2 and EFM3, was not always hindering the optimal habitat
833 conditions based on the recommended thresholds [58]. However, the literature suggests
834 that these circumstances could not always be favourable for native biota; it may even
835 influence the invasion from non-native species [21, 43]. Such circumstances can be avoided
836 by defining flow regime alteration thresholds that trigger expansion of invasive species.
837 Overall, it is worth mention that EFM5-EMF7 always provided above-average habitat
838 conditions, regardless of the season and life-stages. The combined approach, i.e., EFM8
839 could also guarantee above-average habitat conditions, except for adults during Spring
840 season when the long-term temporal failure rate of ensuring above-average habitat
841 conditions was 23% of the time. Adults resulted in being the most vulnerable life-stage due
842 to water diversion, mainly during Spring season. In this context, shallow water HMUs
843 suffered the highest habitat loss. Runoff reduction and the hydropower plant operation in
844 full capacity during Spring season explain extensive habitat loss and vulnerability of the
845 adults life-stage. Conversely, during the Summer season, because most of the time, the
846 available discharge was lower than minimum turbine discharge, the hydropower was not
847 working, and therefore, less habitat loss occurred. Furthermore, during the Summer season
848 except for three first EFMs and EFM9, the rest of the applied EFMs provided quite similar
849 habitat conditions.

850

851 **4.3 Running the hydropower sustainably**

852 Sustainable development and operation of RoR hydropower plants require taking into
853 account not only the economic factor, i.e., profitability which was a common practice in

854 earlier times ago but other factors as well, such as social and environmental impacts [2].
855 Concerning the economic and environmental factors (i.e., flow regime alteration and habitat
856 availability), which were the main focus of this study, results show that adequate e-flows
857 setting poses a crucial task in reaching an agreement among both factors. Yet, the solution
858 is not straightforward; insights from this study highlighted that there is no single EFM that
859 could both maximise hydropower production and guarantee optimal habitat conditions at
860 all seasons and life-stages simultaneously. However, results suggest that if the objective was
861 to maximise the hydropower production while above-average or maintaining quasi-optimal
862 habitat conditions [58], most of the EFMs supported this objective for three life-stages of
863 barbel fish during the wet period. Nevertheless, only a few of the applied EFMs could support
864 the same objective during the low-flow period.

865 Multivariate analysis demonstrated that notably, EFM8 but also EFM9 allowed for
866 reasonable hydropower production by imposing less than 50% of habitat loss for the three
867 life-stages. Nevertheless, other EFMs, e.g., EFM1, EFM2, EFM3, and EFM4, could be other
868 potential alternatives in reaching an agreement among economic and environmental
869 objectives. However, as mentioned above, their performance towards hydropower
870 production was profoundly affected by the flow variability and constrained by specific fish's
871 life-stages. Moreover, it depends on which objective we give more priority, e.g., if we decide
872 to give more priority hydropower production, then EFM1-EFM3 are the best option. In
873 contrast, if we give more priority to riverine ecosystem conservation, instead of fixed
874 minimum e-flows for the entire year, we would suggest applying a dynamic approach similar
875 to EFM9 or EFM8. Nevertheless, the portion of the flow that would be released as e-flows
876 should be carefully adjusted based on the geomorphological features of the river and type
877 of biota to be well-preserved [21, 61]. This study and previous studies [26, 27, 36], have
878 shown that it is possible to reach a reasonable agreement between hydropower production
879 and river conservation; nonetheless, that conclusion may be valid only for the current
880 climate conditions. Taking into account climate change, additional measures should take
881 place to preserve the aquatic ecosystem, such as shutting down the hydropower during
882 critical periods [17] or building instream structures to improve the habitat conditions [62].
883 However, the aforementioned measures may not always be economically feasible.
884 Alternatively, energy mix, e.g., integrating photovoltaics into RoR hydropower plants have
885 shown great potential, not only in maximising the hydropower production while reducing
886 the environmental impacts but also in retaining a considerable volume of water to be used
887 for other purposes, as well [63, 64]. In this regard, future research is needed in exploring
888 possible integration of other conventional/non-conventional renewable energy sources with
889 RoR hydropower.

890

891 **5 Conclusions**

892 RoR hydropower is gaining high-interest world-wide, nevertheless is twofold important to
893 fulfil energy demand sustainably. Such interdisciplinary studies, like ours, are crucial to

894 provided evidence-based management recommendations that may guide water managers
895 to develop operational rules that would support both hydropower production and riverine
896 ecosystem conservation in existing and planned RoR hydropower plants. Considering the
897 limited number of interdisciplinary studies with a focus on RoR hydropower production
898 maximisation and riverine ecosystem conservation, this study shed light in the potential
899 solution that can reconcile such conflicting interests. Namely, the findings of this study
900 suggest that on the one hand, neglecting the RoR hydropower impact on the aquatic
901 ecosystem due to inadequate e-flows setting might not be a good practice, particularly in
902 Mediterranean rivers. On the other hand, e-flows should be carefully defined in order not to
903 compromise the hydropower profitability. The main conclusions drawn from this study are
904 as follows:

905

- 906 • Flow duration curve based EFMs (EFM1 and EFM2), and One-third of the Average
907 Summer Flow: 1/3ASF (EFM3) allowed for the highest hydropower production during
908 four seasons, while providing reasonable e-flow releases during the wet periods only.
- 909 • Monthly minimum-based EFMs, notably EFM5-EFM7, except for the Summer season
910 allowed the highest e-flow releases meanwhile putting considerable restriction into
911 the hydropower production.
- 912 • High e-flow releases did not necessarily provide the highest habitat
913 availability/suitability, and conversely, lower e-flow releases did not always hinder
914 the habitat conditions.
- 915 • Adults life-stage showed to be more vulnerable to water diversion, and the most
916 critical season was Spring.
- 917 • As expected, shallow water HMUs such as riffles, slackwater and run, resulted in
918 being highly sensitive to the water diversion, whereas pools were less impacted.
- 919 • Overall, especially combined e-flow method (EFM8) and daily minimum or so-called
920 dynamic approach (i.e., EFM9), although not the highest, could still provide
921 reasonable hydropower production while imposing less than 50% habitat loss and
922 flow regime alteration for three life-stages of barbel fish most of the time.

923

924 Given these findings, RoR hydropower should be carefully planned and operated by taking
925 into account the riverine ecosystem needs in order to be promoted as a fully sustainable
926 energy source. It is worth highlighting that although the proposed methodological approach
927 was applied at only one study case, it may be still applied to any study case since it was based
928 on well-recognised methodologies applied in similar study cases. Despite that, it is also
929 confessed that there are still some limitations and other issues worth investigating that
930 should be considered in future studies. Finally, the solution-oriented findings resulted from
931 this study, as well as the methodological approach itself, may be relevant to hydropower
932 managers and decision-makers from energy and freshwater conservation sectors by assisting
933 them in reforming the current and future RoR hydropower development policies.

934

935

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